

A new method for construction of duplexes of non-alternant graphs and calculation of topological bond order

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A method for construction of the duplex of a graph involving odd cycles has been developed and its utility in the determination of topological bond order has been shown. The method is general; however, for a particular case of bond orders at (5, n) ring fusions, where $n = 3, 5, 7, \dots$, the method has been shown to be further simplified, ultimately leading to an easy scheme for construction of the subgraphs required for bond order calculation.

The relation between Hückel molecular orbital (HMO) theory and graph theory is well known^{1,2}. The π -bond orders in HMO theory are obtainable³ from the cardinalities of the hydrogen-suppressed molecular graphs of conjugated systems. The method of calculation requires the duplexes⁴ of the corresponding graphs. In case of alternant systems⁵ the duplex is just a duplicate of the original graph but it is not so in case of non-alternant systems, i.e. conjugated systems having odd-membered rings. Although general computer method for getting the adjacency matrix of the duplex of a graph is known, it is desirable to have an easy method for construction of the duplex graph itself. One such algorithm is developed in the present work and its utility in the calculation of topological bond order has been shown. In particular, the bond orders at (5, n) ring fusions, where $n = 3, 5, 7, \dots$ have been shown, on the basis of the present method, to be obtainable from an easy scheme of construction of the relevant subgraphs of the duplexes. The organisation of the paper is as follows : in Section 1, the cardinality of a graph has been defined and the method of its calculation has been briefly outlined for ready reference. In Section 2, the duplex of a graph has been explained and its relation to topological bond order has been mentioned. In Section 3, an algorithm has been proposed for construction of the duplex of a graph containing odd cycles, and an illustration has been given. In Section 4, topological bond orders at the (5, n) ring fusion bond ($n = 3, 5, 7, \dots$) have been calculated and it has been shown that construction of the subgraphs of the duplexes necessary for this calculation follows an easy scheme.

Section 1. Cardinality of a graph :

Two vertices of a graph are said to be 'independent' if

they are not connected by an edge. A collection of vertices of a graph is called an 'independent set' if no two vertices of the set are connected. The number of such independent sets of a graph (G) is called⁵ its 'cardinality' and is denoted by $\sigma(G)$. For example, the following is the independent set of vertices of G_1 (Fig. 1),

$$\{\phi, (1), (2), (3), (4), (1, 3), (1, 4), (3, 4), (1, 3, 4)\}$$

Here ϕ denotes the null set and $\sigma(G_1) = 9$. If the vertices 3

Fig. 1. Two small graphs illustrating the decrease of cardinality with increase in connectedness of vertices

and 4 are joined, the resulting graph is G_2 (Fig. 1). Obviously, $\sigma(G_2)$ must be less than $\sigma(G_1)$ owing to the connectedness of 3 and 4. The independent set of G_2 is

$$\{\phi, (1), (2), (3), (4), (1, 3), (1, 4)\}$$

and $\sigma(G_2) = 7$. However, direct counting is tedious and not desirable for large graphs. A recursive procedure⁷ is briefly outlined below.

By direct counting it can be readily verified that cardinality of a path graph (P_n) with n vertices is given by the recurrence relation,

$$\sigma(P_n) = \sigma(P_{n-1}) + \sigma(P_{n-2}) \quad (1)$$

which is similar to the relation for Fibonacci⁸ numbers,

$$F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}, F_0 = 1, F_1 = 1 \quad (2)$$

It can also be readily verified that

$$\sigma(P_n) = F_{n+1} \quad (3)$$

Some illustrations showing the validity of eqns. (1), (2) and (3) are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Cardinalities of path graphs by direct counting and their relation to Fibonacci-numbers

Number of vertices n	P_n	Independent set	$\sigma(P_n)$	F_{n+1}
1		$\{\phi, *\}$	2	2
2		$\{\phi, (1), (2)\}$	3	3
3		$\{\phi, (1), (2), (3), (1, 3)\}$	5	5
4		$\{\phi, (1), (2), (3), (4), (1, 3), (1, 4), (2, 4)\}$	8	8
5		$\{\phi, (1), (2), (3), (4), (5), (1, 3), (1, 4), (1, 5), (2, 4), (2, 5), (3, 5), (1, 3, 5)\}$	13	13

For more complicated graphs the recurrence⁷ relation is,

$$\sigma(G) = \sigma(G-p) + \sigma(G-p-A_p) \quad (4)$$

where p is any vertex of the graph G and A_p is the set of

Fig. 2. An illustration of the subgraphs required in eqn. (4).

vertices connected by an edge to p as shown in Fig. 2. Eqns. (3) and (4) are to be used in conjunction with the relation,

$$\sigma(G) = \prod_{i=1}^n \sigma(G_i) \quad (5)$$

where G consists of disjoint subgraphs $G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n$. A sample calculation of cardinality of the H-suppressed molecular graph (G_N) of naphthalene is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Graph and subgraphs required for calculation of cardinality of the naphthalene graph.

As $\sigma(P_9) = F_{10} = 89$ and $[\sigma(P_3)]^2 = F_4^2 = 25$, one gets

from eqns. (4) and (5), $\sigma(G_N) = 114$.

Section 2. Duplex of a graph and topological bond order in non-alternant hydrocarbons (NAH) :

The duplex of a graph G is defined as a graph G^D such that the corresponding adjacency matrices $A(G)$ and $A(G^D)$ are related⁹ as

$$A(G^D) = \frac{\text{O} \mid A(G)}{A(G) \mid \text{O}} \quad (6)$$

As an illustration we consider the 3-membered cycle C_3 (Fig. 5). The adjacency matrices of C_3 and its duplex are

$$A(C_3) = \begin{matrix} & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ \begin{matrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \text{ and } A(C_3^D) = \begin{matrix} & 1 & 2 & 3 & 1' & 2' & 3' \\ \begin{matrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 1' \\ 2' \\ 3' \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \quad (7)$$

The graph C_3^D whose adjacency matrix is $A(C_3)$ is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The 3-cycle and its duplex.

The topological bond order between the p -th and q -th vertices of a NAH has been shown⁴ to be

$$\Pi_{pq} = \frac{\sigma(G^D - p - A_p) + \sigma(G^D - q' - A'_q)}{2\sigma(G^D - p - q')} \quad (8)$$

where G^D is the duplex of the hydrogen-suppressed graph of the NAH and (p, q') is the edge of the duplex which corresponds to the edge (p, q) in the parent graph.

Section 3. An algorithm for construction of duplex of a NAH graph :

From the preceding discussions it is felt that an easy method of construction of the duplex of a graph is necessary. We propose the following algorithm :

Step 1. Delete an edge (a, b) in each of the odd rings; the edge must not be common with an even ring.

Step 2. Duplicate the resulting graph in a reverse orientation.

Step 3. Join a to b' and a' to b . The resulting graph required duplex.

Fig. 5. Some illustrations of construction of duplexes by the present algorithm.

Some illustrations are given in Fig. 5.

Section 4. Calculation of topological bond order at the (5, n) ring fusion bonds :

We first consider a conjugated system whose molecular graph consists of a five- and a three-membered ring fused together (graph G_4 of Fig. 5). The (5, 3) ring fusion bond corresponds to the edge joining the vertices a and b in G_4 . To calculate the topological bond order using eqn. (8), the necessary subgraphs are $G_4^D - a - A_a$, $G_4^D - b' - A_b$ (which are the same owing to symmetry) and $G_4^D - a - b'$. These

Fig. 6. Subgraphs of G_4^D and their cardinalities required for utilisation of eqn. (8) in calculating the bond order of (5, 3) ring fusion bond.

subgraphs and their breaking up according to eqns. (1)–(5) for calculation of their cardinalities are shown in Fig. 6. Thus,

$$\sigma(G_4^D - a - A_a) = \sigma(G_4^D - b - A_b) = 59$$

and $\sigma(G_4^D - a - b') = 160$, which yield from eqn. (8), $\pi_{ab} = 0.369$. From a direct diagonalisation of the Hückel matrix the π -bond order for the (a, b) bond comes out to be 0.374.

The subgraphs necessary for calculation of topological bond orders at $(5, n)$ (n odd) ring fusion bonds (a, b) are shown in Fig. 7. It is readily observed that these subgraphs are easy to construct : $G^D - a - A_a$ consists of a linear chain P_7 with linear branches of lengths $(n-3)$ and $(n-2)$, respectively, at positions 3 and 4. $G^D - a - b$ requires the linear chain P_8 with a linear branch of length $(n-2)$ at each of the positions 4 and 5.

Fig. 7. Subgraphs of the duplexes of some $(5, n)$ fused ring systems (n odd) for calculation of bond order of the ring-fusion bonds.

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